

Energy Configuration Derivation of the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein Distributions

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Statistical mechanics texts (1) provide a quick derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor $\exp(-e/T)$ by expanding $W(E-e)$, where $W(E)$ is the number of energy arrangements of N particles whose energies sum to E . A first order Taylor series expansion yields $\exp(-e/T)$ provided $e \ll T$. In this note, we extend these ideas to the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions.

Number of States Approach to Statistical Mechanics

Statistical mechanics is often presented in terms of “counting states with different single particle energy arrangements” as these states may occur in nature. In fact, each arrangement is usually given a weight of 1 meaning that one is assuming complete uncertainty as to which state the system is in at an instant in time. A traditional derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution (1) is given as follows. Let $W(E)$ be the number of energy arrangements of N particles whose energies sum to E . Then, remove one particle with energy e and calculate $W(E-e)$ using a first order Taylor series:

$$W(E-e) = W(E) - e \frac{d}{de} W(E) = W(E) [1 - e \frac{d}{de} \ln(W)] \quad ((1))$$

If $(d/de \ln(W))$ is called $1/T$ and $e \ll T$, then: $W(E-e)/W(E) = f(e) = \exp(-e/T)$. ((2))

It is usually not stressed that $e \ll T$ for this derivation to hold. Experimentally, however, the Maxwell-Boltzmann form $\exp(-e/T)$ has been found to hold for e about 5 times T . The approach, however, is interesting and it seems it may be applied to the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions, although this does not seem to be commonly done, at least in texts.

Fermi-Dirac Case

Consider an N particle Fermi-Dirac system with one particle per energy level (spin ignored). The ground state then consists of placing the particles into the first N energy levels. Thus, E_0 is the energy level of the last particle (to give it a name). If the ground state receives a large amount of energy, one may imagine various particles leaving their ground state energy levels and moving into higher levels. This then leads to many different types of single particle energy arrangements. The goal is to find the number of energy arrangements associated with moving a particle out of a ground state level e_i into higher levels. This number may be associated with $1-f(e_i)$ i.e. the probability of the state e_i being empty, where $f(e_i)$ is the probability that it is occupied.

First, one needs to have the state e_i occupied, which occurs with a probability of $f(e_i)$. Next, a minimum amount of energy $E_0 - e_i$ is needed to bring the particle from e_i into a state “above the ground state” energy range. Imagine there is E_1 extra energy above the ground state of thermal energy available. Then, moving a particle from e_i to E_0 has already consumed $E_0 - e_i$ of this energy. Thus, lower e_i particles consume more energy than higher e_i particles.

Let $W[E - (E_0 - e_i)]$ be the number of states associated with the remaining thermal energy. This then serves as a measure of the energy arrangements available to the particle originally in e_i . Using the same arguments as in the Maxwell-Boltzmann section:

$$W(E - E_0 + e_i) = W(E - E_0) + e_i \frac{d}{de} W = W(E - E_0) [1 + e_i \left(\frac{d}{de} \ln(W(E - E_0)) \right)] \quad ((3))$$

If one calls $\left(\frac{d}{de} \ln(W(E - E_0)) \right) = 1/T$ and $e_i \ll T$, then one has $W(E - E_0) \exp(e_i/T)$.

Thus: $((4)) \quad 1 - f(e_i) = f(e_i) \exp(e_i/T) = \text{probability for the state } e_i \text{ to be empty}$

This in turn yields the Fermi-Dirac distribution.

Bose-Einstein Case

For the Bose-Einstein case, one may note that if there are $f(e_i)$ bosons in a state e_i , then the probability is enhanced by $f(e_i)!$ as shown in (2). Thus, adding an extra boson changes the probability to $(f(e_i) + 1)!$ so there is an enhancement for scattering into e_i of $f(e_i) + 1$ which is very different from Maxwell-Boltzmann scattering. Consider a system of N bosons and a total energy of E . Let $W(E)$ be the number of arrangements (including the $f(e_i)!$ factors) of the N particles. A particle of energy e is removed and one may calculate the effect:

$W(E - e_i)/W(E)$ is associated with $f(e_i)$, but adding the extra particle back brings in an additional $f(e_i) + 1$ factor. Thus, it seems that:

$$W(E - e_i)/W(E) (1 + f(e_i)) = f(e_i) \quad ((5))$$

This in turn leads to the Bose-Einstein distributions as $W(E - e_i)/W(E) = 1 - e_i/T = \exp(-e_i/T)$ if $e_i \ll T$.

If the enhancement rule were $(1 + f(e_i))^q$, one would change $((5))$ to be $W(E - e_i)/W(E) (1 + f(e_i))^q$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to present energy configuration arguments for the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions. We argue that the $\exp(-e/T)$ or $\exp(e/T)$ factors arise from first order Taylor expansions of $W(E - e_i)$ or $W(E + e_i)$ where $W(E)$ is the number of energy arrangements of N particles with total energy E . The first order Taylor expansion only applies if $e \ll T$. This

perhaps allows one to view the FD and BE distributions without using grand canonical partition functions or reaction balance.

References

1. Reif, F. Fundamentals of Statistical and Thermal Physics (McGraw Hill, New York, 1965)
2. Feynman, R. Lecture Notes https://www.feynmanlectures.caltech.edu/III_04.html